

The Buddhist Nuns of 4th - 6th century China

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The earliest Buddhist nuns in China lived between the 4th and 6th centuries AD. We have record of their lives from Baochang's compilation of their biographies in 516 AD. They were women who were more likely than not of elite literati familial origin. Many of them were centered around the great metropolitan cities of Chang'an and Luoyang in the North, and Jiankang in the south. The earliest nuns adopted Buddhist ideas and practices that had been slowly entering China along the Silk Routes from Central Asia and India. In the several hundred years prior to the 4th century, Buddhism was quite limited in China, practiced more or less by residents of foreign origin. These residents were treated as marginal within the larger cultural milieu. In particular, the Han dynasty ending in 220 AD had little use for Buddhist ideas and practices, as they were heavily invested in Confucian orthodoxies concerning family, institutions, and statecraft. The conquest of the northern capital cities of Luoyang and Chang'an in 311 and 316 AD by a united nomadic Xiongnu alliance meant an end to Han Chinese governance in the north. Gentry who survived the massacres and book-burnings in the capital cities fled to Jiankang in the south, in present-day Nanjing, where they set up a new seat of government. This massive societal crisis threw the assured Confucian orthodoxies into disarray. In the vacuum of political theory, intellectuals held salons or qingtans to discuss speculative new forms of political and natural philosophy. This is the setting for the broader uptake and flowering of Buddhist ideas and practices, which often took the form of Buddho-Daoist syntheses. The earliest Buddhist nuns were living in this context. In response to the social turmoil of the times, these women bucked Confucian ideas of the exemplary woman as primarily devoted to the institutions of family and, in connection with the apparatus of state, the familial-dynasty. Importantly, the institution of the family should not be seen here as a "private" arena, as it is organized in modern secular societies with a distinction between private and public. In the 4-6th centuries, the family as an institution was the primary building block of political economy. Noble houses interfaced with each other and also with an imperial apparatus of state in alliances involving power, prestige, and territorial control (ie. economic output). The family sent sons into the imperial officialdom; daughters participated in various political alliances between houses. This is the setting in which we can see how radical the Buddhist nuns were. They were trail-blazers innovating new practices that took care of people who fell into the interstitial spaces between the various norms, practices, and institutions of family and familial dynasty. These innovations played an important part in shifting the entire social system, introducing the institution of the sangha in addition to, and in relation with, the institutions of state and family.

Date Range: 300 CE - 516 CE

Region: The Buddhist Nuns' China

Region tags: China, Six Dynasties China, Early Medieval China

China of 300-516 AD. The nuns were primarily concentrated along the Yellow River toward Xi'an and Luoyang. They were also present along the Huai River and along the Eastern parts of the Yangtze River Delta. Some nuns may have made it further West along the Silk Road. There was also scattered presence around Guangdong. The map area drawn focuses on where there was a main concentration of

nuns, along the rivers starting from around Xi'an in the west moving northeastward toward the coast; and stretching southward toward the Yangtze River Delta and Jiankang (present-day Nanjing).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Tsai, Kathryn Ann, trans. *Lives of the Nuns: Biographies of Chinese Buddhist Nuns from the Fourth to Sixth Centuries*, A translation of the *Pi-ch'iu-ni chuan*, compiled by Shih Pao-ch'ang. University of Hawaii Press, 1994.
- Source 2: Ebrey, Patricia. *Women and the Family in Chinese History*. Taylor and Francis Group, 2002.
- Source 3: Zurcher, Erik. *The Buddhist Conquest of China: The Spread and Adaptation of Buddhism in Early Medieval China*. Brill, 2007.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://asiasociety.org/education/women-traditional-china>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://tripitaka.cbeta.org>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Xi'an was a cosmopolitan center and would have been a site of cultural exchange along the Silk Road. Many ideas and practices passed through Xi'an and Luoyang from Central Asia to the West and from the riverine ways of life to the East.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Cultural contact *could* be competitive. So for instance, the interaction between the nomadic horse-born people of the northern grasslands and the settled, agrarian societies (of which our Buddhist nuns were a part) was famously antagonistic. That being said, cosmopolitan centers like Xi'an would have been more pluralistic, and many codes and creeds would have existed side by side. See Erik Zurcher, *The Buddhist Conquest of China* (Brill, 1972) for an account of the bloody conflicts in 311 and 316 AD between the nomadic people (Xiongnu) and the Han Chinese.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Xi'an would have been pluralistic, being such a cosmopolitan city. Traders from Central Asia and the kingdom of Sogdia would have been present in significant numbers in Xi'an, and they lived in ethnic enclaves / communities within the capital city. See Étienne de la Vaissière, *Sogdian Traders: A History* (Brill, 2005)

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The Xiongnu (also named the "Hun" - Xiongnu is a rather offensive moniker meaning "fierce slave," but it's still frequently used) and the Han Chinese were constantly in conflict. There were instances of the Xiongnu being brought into the armies or militias of warlords as fighters, as happened in the early 4th century when the Sima princes were fighting each other (and so it would seem, a sort of collaboration). But the threat of ethnic loyalties was ever-present, especially since the Xiongnu (the sinicized Huns) who lived within Chinese territory were often poorly treated. By the first decade of the fourth century AD in China, "the Xiongnu troops in China had become thoroughly familiar with Chinese military methods and strategy during the civil wars between the Sima Warlords, who had not hesitated to rely upon Liu Yuan's [a thoroughly sinicized Xiongnu nobleman] assistance in their work of mutual extermination, and who, moreover, had often reinforced their own armies with foreign mercenaries and slaves." Zurcher, *The Buddhist Conquest of China*, 83.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There was violent conflict with groups to the north of China. The Xiongnu and the Jie had established independent states north of China. There were ways to encourage peace and collaboration: sometimes the Xiongnu were brought into Han enclaves as soldiers, and there were aristocratic marriage alliances between them and the Han. So in the instance of the Xiongnu, they were both an external group and also internal to Han society (as the previous note about their incorporation within competing Sima princely factions also attests to). But the threat of conflict was ever present and sometimes flared up very violently, as occurred in 311 and 316 AD.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: The narratives of the Buddhist nuns show that coming to the order was very much not assigned at birth, but rather was a volitional transition for many. For instance the nun Seng Tuan escaped to the convent three days before her marriage day to seek entry into the order.

Baochang, *Lives of the Nuns*, 49-50.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: The biographies record a very explicit conversation between the nun An Ling Shou (fourth century) and her father about how her choice to become a nun did not run counter to filial piety. Baochang, *Lives of the Nuns*, 20.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: While it cannot be said that the nuns were in any way assigned to the order as a function of class, it should be said that the nuns in the biographies are by and large a very elite set. Many of them were very literate, and they would have been provided their literati educations through the auspices of their natal families.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Many of the nuns spoken of in the biographies were quite young -- so they would have found themselves released from wifely and motherly duties.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddhist nuns differed from their monastic counterparts in several respects. One main issue was that the burden of moral responsibility for the virtue of chastity fell more on the women than the men, and so the nuns were more restricted in how they could travel -- vulnerable as they were to banditry by armed robbers, rape, etc. This asymmetrical burden of responsibility also meant that they were less able to perform the various ascetic dhutanga practices held to be exemplary for monks (such as that of being out in the wilds for a long time).

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Some practices were typical of nuns - chanting, memorizing sutras, etc. There were also concentration exercises, such that some nuns looked like lumps of wood or stone. It must also be observed that practices of self-mutilation were observed, such as the burning of fingers and the practice of self-immolation in the name of the Buddha.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: There was an instance of legitimizing encounter/exchange when some nuns arrived in China from Sri Lanka sometime around 434 AD. An officiating/legitimizing function was also performed by two monks who travelled to China from Central Asia and India: Gunavarman, who died in 431 AD, and Sanghavarman, who died in 442 AD.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Some nuns had hundreds of disciples and followers. Other nuns were influential in high places, for instance teaching Emperor Wu and his sons (as the nuns Hui Chung, Seng Ching, Miao Chih, and Chih Sheng did, among others)

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: A number of nuns had the ear of Emperor Wu and his descendants. These imperial scions provided for the material well-being of the nuns, built convents for them, gifted lands for the purpose of burial rites, and invited the nuns to teach.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Some nuns were indeed supported by the scions of Emperor Wu.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: There is reference to convents being built for nuns, as well as land for burial sites being marked off.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The imperial apparatus (with emperors, concubines, and a genealogy of familial-dynastic descent) is markedly different from the Buddhist nuns and monk's order.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: There was a separation of politics and religious life, even though some nuns were influential and taught political officials.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: The institution still was quite voluntarist at this time.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: It's true that the sanghas were a way for men to escape corvee labor obligations to the state. For this reason, however, sanghas were frequently experiencing culling and diminishment in number through so-called "selections," for the state wanted to preserve its labor tax base.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 500000

Notes: In the region of Chang'an (Xi'an) in 299AD, there was about 1 million people, of which about half was of foreign origin (Xiongnu and other). Zurcher, *Buddhist Conquest of China*, 81. Starting at around 2 AD and going through 516 AD, one estimate suggests that there may have been about 60 million people total in China. See http://afe.easia.columbia.edu/special/china_1950_population.htm and in particular the graphic by Vaclav Smil, *China's Environmental Crisis* (1993). But this number is contested. Kent Deng uses official Chinese censuses and tax records from medieval times (the state administered the collection of grain tax as well as labor tax on villages). His estimate of Chinese population as registered by official records is much lower -- roughly 29 million in 520 AD. The range for the time span under consideration (280-520 AD) is roughly 18-29 million people. Kent Deng, "Unveiling China's True Population Statistics for the Pre-Modern Era with Official Census Data", *Population Review* 43, no. 2 (2004): 32-69 Then, there is a guess about Buddhists as a percentage of total population: "Both the indigenous texts used in *The Buddhist Conquest of China* and the Chinese literature translated from Indian originals were confined to a small but influential minority of Chinese people, somewhere

between 2 and 5% of the total population." Stephen Teiser's forward in Zürcher, *The Buddhist Conquest of China*, xv. If we take the population of China between 300-516 AD to be on the order of 25mm people, per Kent Deng's estimates, then using the 2-5% guideline suggested by Teiser, we get roughly half a million people to 1.25 million people (tops) in China under the influence of Buddhist ideas and practices. If we assume that men and women were equally persuaded by Buddhist ideas and practices, and also assume that there were roughly the same number of men and women living at the time (this is not to be taken for granted given the various violent conflicts) -- then we may think that something on the order of 250,000 and 625,000 Buddhist nuns were living at any given moment between 300-516 AD. Now, there would have been more Buddhist nuns toward the later part of the time range, and fewer nuns toward the beginning, since the Buddhist order was just getting established at this time.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2

Notes: "Both the indigenous texts used in *The Buddhist Conquest of China* and the Chinese literature translated from Indian originals were confined to a small but influential minority of Chinese people, somewhere between 2 and 5% of the total population." Stephen Teiser's forward in Zürcher, *The Buddhist Conquest of China*, xv. If we take the population of China between 300-516 AD to be on the order of 25mm people, per Kent Deng's estimates, then using the 2-5% guideline suggested by Teiser, we get roughly half a million people to 1.25 million people (tops) in China under the influence of Buddhist ideas and practices. If we assume that men and women were equally persuaded by Buddhist ideas and practices, and also assume that there were roughly the same number of men and women living at the time (this is not to be taken for granted given the various violent conflicts) -- then we may think that something on the order of 250,000 and 625,000 Buddhist nuns were living at any given moment between 300-516 AD. Now, there would have been more Buddhist nuns toward the later part of the time range, and fewer nuns toward the beginning, since the Buddhist order was just getting established at this time.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: Nuns are recognized for their expertise -- for their learnedness, as well as their soundness of advice and the virtuosity of their practices. Certain nuns are definitely recognized as excellent or exemplary, and there is informal hierarchy in the sense of some nuns being seen as more aspirational vis-a-vis others.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There were many convents in existence at the same time period. It seems that these were local communities, and each had exemplary nuns or founding members. But these are not ranked hierarchically, across communities. The caveat here is to say that some influential nuns were noble-born, and had access to people inhabiting the imperial state system: this would have been an informal sort of hierarchy.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

Notes: It seems that each local community had their exemplary persons. The nuns answered to the monks as well and accepted their precept obligations from the Assembly of Monks. But it does seem that nuns were able to overturn monks' objections. See this genesis story of the first nun in China: "The foreign Buddhist monk T'an-mo-chieh-to set up a ceremonial dais [on which Ching-chien and her disciples were to accept all of the monastic rules for some nas found in the newly translated text.] The Chinese monk Shih Tao-ch'ang objected to this action, however, on the basis of scriptures on the origins of monastic rules that said that, because there was no Assembly of Nuns in China to bestow the rules on the women as the scriptures required, the ritual should not be carried out. His objections were not acknowledged and, as a result, [Shih Tao-Ch'ang] took a boat down the Ssu River to the south. Ching-chien an the others, four together, became Buddhist nuns by accepting, from the Assembly of Monks only, the obligation to observe all the monastic rules." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 19.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: There is some indication of the efficacy of individual deeds. For instance: in Seng Tuan's escape to a convent in her efforts to get out of marriage arrangements. After a great deal of crying and chanting scripture, her bride-groom was gored by an ox, and Seng Tuan was able to enter the sangha.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: The nuns are actively involved in teaching and transmitting their knowledge. And they seek legitimating teachers as well -- for instance teachers coming from Central Asia and Sri Lanka.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders of a community are considered fallible in the sense that in teacher-student relations, teachers are considered fallible. Over and over the monastic setting is presented as sites of formation, as an educational setting.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: "Charges of fallibility" here would sometimes be implicit -- as when a student doesn't recognize a teacher as particularly exemplary in such-and-such a way. Hence, some nuns attracted hundreds of students, and they are written up as exemplary. This would not have been the case for all nuns.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: The political system would ask for sangha selection to cull un-learned nuns and monks. So there is consistently recognition that the order of nuns and of monks were composed of fallible humans.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Lotus Sutra is read and chanted over and over by the nuns. There are other texts circulating as well.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Texts were not only copied and transcribed; they were also chanted. Nuns were recognized for chanting texts very quickly -- for instance the nun Chih Hsien, who was able to chant all of the Lotus Sutra in a day and a night. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 22

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: If one takes exemplars, like Siddhartha Gautama, to be "semi-divine" -- then perhaps one could say that the answer to this question is "yes." That is, scriptures are thought of as being the words of exemplary persons -- Siddhartha first among them. These people inspire love and devotion, and inspire many subsequent people to be *like them*

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Scriptures were understood as originating from India, from communities. Central Asian and Sri Lankan teachers were valued as able to explicate scriptures.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: There are canonical scriptures important to the nuns, like the Lotus Sutra. But that doesn't mean that they were not open to other texts.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Between AD 307-313, "there were at least 42 Buddhist institutions in Luoyang." In the South, "Seven monasteries were established in Jiankang between 343-372." In 379 the famous Buddhist monk Dao'an returned to the north from Jiankang to Chang'an -- he had fled previously. On Dao'an's account, "there was a five-story pagoda in the capital" (Nancy Steinhardt, *Chinese Architecture in a Time of Turmoil, 200-600 AD*, 122). It is worth noting that pagodas were built to house relics (sharira). By the early sixth century in Luoyang and Chang'an, the pagodas did not look like circular, egg-dome shaped Central or South Asian stupas. We can look at the example of Songyuesi in Henan, on the eastern periphery of Luoyang. This was a dodecagonal building, built in 523 AD; a palace had sat on the site between 508-511 AD, and a Buddhist monastery inhabited the grounds in 484 AD. (Nancy Steinhardt, *Chinese Architecture in a Time of Turmoil, 200-600 AD*, 202). The example of the pagoda Yongningsi in Luoyang is also instructive (516-534 AD). This was a very tall four-sided pagoda made of wood. It caught fire and burned down in 534 AD.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 40

Notes: Songyuesi was 39.8m tall. Nancy Steinhardt, *Chinese Architecture in a Time of Turmoil, 200-600 AD*, 202.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: There was an evolution of the kinds of buildings used to house relics of Buddhist monks and nuns. The Mogao caves in Dunhuang began construction in 366 AD -- these exemplify a genre of Buddhist cave temple. Nancy Steinhardt, *Chinese Architecture in a Time of Turmoil, 200-600 AD*, 115. East of that, in Xi'an and Luoyang, there were tall pagodas built by the early 6th century. Dao'an reports a small five-story pagoda in the 4th century. Pagodas were sometimes built for or by nuns. For instance, a man built a "foreign-style pagoda" for Shih Hui-Chiung. Tsai, 43. The nun Pao ying was responsible for building a 5-story pagoda in the 5th century. Tsai, 58. Tan hui built a pagoda and large temple complex in the fifth century. Tsai, 94.

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Pagodas

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Relics (sharira) were considered sacred. They were buried and sometimes held in temples or pagodas

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Pagodas and towers must have been oriented to various aspects of the landscape -- mountains and rivers, etc -- though I don't have further details.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: There are accounts of monks traveling to India through Central Asia on pilgrimage; for example Faxian in 400 AD. But whether or not nuns travelled to India is not known; they are not mentioned in the biographies of eminent nuns. Since nuns were vulnerable to banditry along the roads (and unwanted kidnapping and attention), nuns were not able to travel alone as readily as their male counterparts. The burden of chastity was higher as well on the women. Indeed, I think this is the reason that the ascetic practices differ between men and women -- men in the Biographies of Eminent Monks are more frequently cited as engaging in extreme practices in the wild places, a practice not mentioned in the Biographies of the Nuns.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: There are ideas that some trace or echo may survive the death of the physical body -- karma theory is involved in this -- imbedded within the doctrine of paticca-samuppada as a theory of causality normatively directed toward the end of suffering. So that is to say that there may be afterlives of the actions that people take, in the sense of "consequences" -- "effects," in the cause and effect cycle of paticca-samuppada. But, such consequences or effects are importantly different from the idea that "personhood" or "consciousness" might survive the physical body. It may be that some practitioners thought this, but it is not imbedded within the doctrine of paticca-samuppada as I understand it, and as far as I can tell from my reading of the text it is not how many of the early Chinese Buddhist nuns took it. (There is talk, in two biographies, of reaching the "Western Paradise" or "Tushita Heaven" -- but

what is meant by these modes of speaking is far from clear, see below)

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: A sense of afterlife is not a straightforward concept. There are, for instance, Daoist quests for immortality, as could be seen in the practice of the nun Kuang Ching who ate only pine resin for 15 years. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 51. Such practices are revealing of an attitude toward death as an event to be avoided -- and perhaps by implication, that there is not an aspirational situation after that event-horizon. But, there is a manner of speaking found within the biographies that involves a more "supernatural" take on the afterlife. In one biography, it was said that "In the fourteenth year of the yuan-chia reign period (437) in the tenth month, Hui Yu first carried out a seven-day austerity fast and then made a vow, saying, "If truly the fast I have just completed has its effect so that after I abandon my body in death I will assuredly see the Buddha in his paradise, then may I see, as proof, the radiant light of the Buddha manifest within seven days." (39-40). This is an understanding of cause and effect that relates the austerity measures of fasting to being able to see the Buddha after "abandoning the body." I should like to point out here that the statement is expressed as a conditional -- it is a speculative statement unsure about the existence of the cause-and-effect relation (between fasting and the desired state). In the case of this biography, though, the nun does interpret a sign of light as an indication that the cause-and-effect relation exists. Though one might think, from contemporary interpretations of Buddhist doctrine, that "karma" is a critical idea in Buddhist traditions, in fact the term 'karma' does not appear at all in the text of the biographies of the Chinese Buddhist nuns. I think that this is because the function of having a "karma" theory is already taken care of by a basic theory of causality, a theory of cause and effect. And how different nuns theorize causality, or cause and effect, will vary. These variances will depend on what experiences and ideas they have had exposure to, what other education they had outside of the sangha within their natal family, etc. It is worth saying that other concepts around at the time would have involved issues of family loyalty and etiquette/ethics, ideas of health related to medicinal theories and practices, speculative takes on natural philosophy in Daoist teachings and also in ordinary life (as in the manipulation of waterways for agricultural purposes) etc.

Reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Notes: Though the idea of rebirth is a feature of Buddhist cosmology, it is an open question how different nuns took this idea. The idea of rebirth is found in the case of the nun Fa-sheng and the nun Shih Hsuan-Tsao -- but the other biographies do *not* make extended mention of rebirth. Far more space is devoted to elaborating upon the nuns' life conditions, why they turned to the sangha, their accomplishments in chanting and various support from patrons -- etc. Many biographies spell out the desire to remain unmarried, a quite this-worldly motivation for entering the sangha. Quotes on Fa-sheng and Shih Hsuan Tsao are below, which do make use of the idea of rebirth. But it is unclear whether the destinations referred to (Western Paradise of Amita, Tushita Heaven) are of "this world." "Fa-sheng had always expressed the wish to be reborn in the Western Paradise [of Amita Buddha]. To her sisters in religion, T'an-ching and T'an-ai, she said, "I have devoted myself to following the [Buddhist] way, and my will is fixed on the Western Paradise." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, p. 38 The nun Shih Hsuan-Tsao says: "with constant longing and concentration she vowed to be reborn in the Tushita Heaven [of Maitreya, the next Buddha]." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, p. 42 The idea of rebirth seems to show up more affirmatively in the case of the nun Shan-Miao: "Shan Miao wrapped herself up in the cloth she had woven and had soaked in the oil and set herself on fire. When the flames had reached as high as her head she ordered her sister, "Tell the administrator of the meditation hall to strike the gong to summon all the other nuns that they may come quickly to say farewell because I am now abandoning

this life." She had not yet died by the time all the nuns had arrived in great haste and alarm. Shan-miao said to the nuns gathered there, "Each of you must diligently make the effort to perfect your spiritual life because the cycle of birth and death is a fearsome thing. You must seek to escape it, taking heed not to fall into further transmigration. I have previously abandoned this body as a worship offering to the Buddha twenty-seven times, but it is only this time that I shall attain the first fruit." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, pp. 52-53. My own view is that we should pay attention primarily to ideas of causality, theories of cause and effect, without hunting for "foundational ideas" like rebirth or karma (ie we should see how such ideas are used, when in fact they are used -- and not simply repeated, as they are in the footnotes, because the received tradition thinks that the idea is a foundational one). It may be that ideas of rebirth or karma can be functionally understood as simply indicating something about cause and effect -- including consequences that extend beyond one lifetime (as institutions do, or in the complicated ways in which we remember each other in relationship). In relation to theories of cause and effect or causal efficacy, we can notice that the idea of merit does feature very prominently in the biographies of the nuns. Specifically, this idea is often used in relation to patrons and donors. For instance, the nun Kang Min-Kan speaks of the convent that a patron gifted: "In the great realm of the Chin dynasty all the four Buddhist assemblies of monks, nuns, and male and female householders are now established for the first time. Furthermore, that which you as donor have established will bestow blessings and merit." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 25. In the case of the nun Tao-Ch'iung - "In the tai-yuan period (376-396) of the Eastern Chin dynasty, the empress admired her exalted conduct, and, whenever she wished to gain merit by giving gifts or by listening to religious exhortations, she most often depended on the convent where Tao-ch'iung lived for such opportunities" Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, p. 40. Finally: regarding the six paths or realms of the Wheel of Life – the gods, demi-gods, humans, hungry ghosts, animals, and hell-beings frequently thought of in Buddhist cosmology: these are indeed prominent in Tibetan pictorial uptake of the concept of paticca-samuppada. But we should notice that Tibetan uptake of this doctrine happens in the 7th century AD, after the time of our earliest Buddhist nuns. The earliest known examples of the bhavacakra would be circa the fifth century AD, perhaps the sixth century. The text of the biographies of the Buddhist nuns does not make explicit reference to the six paths (of hungry ghosts, hell realms, etc).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: It seems that nuns' bodies were not cremated, but mostly buried. In the biography of the nun Shih Hui Ch'iung, she instructed her disciples thus "After I die, you should not bury me, but rather give my body to someone to chop it up and feed it to the animals." Because her disciples couldn't bear to chop her up, they simply left her to the elements; reportedly no animals touched her, thus signifying something of her special status. She was buried, and a pagoda was erected for her. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 43. Chinese Buddhists were not often cremated, though nuns did perform self-immolation. In one instance a nun's relics after immolation were placed in a silver jug. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 66. Relics were also buried, as in the case of the nun Ching Kuei. Tsai, 81.

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– I don't know

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: There is an account of a body being left for wild animals -- but in the biography, animals did not touch the body

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: See biography of the nun Shih Hui-Ch'iung, Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, pg. 43.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: A number of Buddhist nuns were described as giving away material goods as soon as they received them -- as in the case of Seng Shu. Tsai 101. It would seem to run against this value of giving away material goods to store them up in a burial site, to be buried with the body.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– I don't know

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– I don't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– I don't know

↳ Other formal burial type:
– Yes [specify]: relics in pagodas

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: The nuns had visions and attached significance to various visions. But I'm not sure these visions are up to the level where they could be called "supernatural." One might think that the Lotus Sutra is full of supernatural beings, so if the Lotus Sutra is accepted by the nuns, then the nuns must also have believed in some sense in the supernatural figures of that text. It is possible to think this, but I tend to think that there is a lot of complicated territory in terms of what nuns accepted in the Sutra -- they must have "theologized" in some way, thought through the various stories of the Sutra -- in much the same way that contemporary readers might read the stories of the Old or New Testaments figuratively, as literature, not completely literally. (Was the earth literally created in 7 days? etc -- not many theologians would take that position -- even though a literal take on that statement would render that text very "supernatural" indeed). In fact, in the biographies of the nuns, reference to the Lotus Sutra (Flower of the Law, in this translation) primarily have to do with nuns accomplishments in chanting it, and chanting it very quickly. I think this practice was valued as a pedagogical matter -- a making

available of the text orally, in a society that highly valued teaching, learning, scholarship, and the literary arts.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Some explications of causality are not clearly "naturalistic" so might be said to be ambiguously "supernatural." For example: the nun Seng Tuan wanted to escape marriage, so ran to a convent where she was given the Bodhisattva Kuan-Shih-Yin Sutra. She chanted, cried, and made prostrations, and after three days she saw a vision of the Buddha announcing to her that her to-be-groom would be gored by an ox. This indeed transpired the next day. This is an instance of there not exactly being a supernatural being, but a *vision*. There is some implication of causality between the chanting and prostrations and the outcome of the groom being gored by an ox, but just how this causality works is not explicit.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist nuns (and monks) are interested in teaching and learning -- this is of a piece with a larger cultural literati milieu, out of which they come. Much literati education as well as the educational practices of the nuns are about formation.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: It's completely unclear to me by what is meant by a "moral" versus "conventional" distinction here. As a thinker I don't accept this distinction as obvious, in the way it would need to be if it were posed as a "poll" sort of question, in everyday language, without any kind of technical framing. The Buddhist nuns had to break with certain kinds of conventions with regard to their roles as daughters, mothers, and wives -- that is, with the institution of the family and in particular the familial dynasty as an institution of political economy. This is to say that the familial dynasty structured social life in that time, so norms, practices, conventions, etc were in service of that structure. The nuns formed a new institution that would have been quite differently oriented from the familial dynasty -- but there are sets of moral conventions in both institutions. Further, those institutions interacted -- the nuns were not totally divorced from their natal families after they left the sangha, and they still would have found compelling the various norms of filiality. An example of this is the nun Fa Sheng, who treated a certain Madame Shan "like her own mother." These two women were not biologically related, so one could say that according to family and family-dynasty norms, it is not necessary, super-erogatory, to treat someone not-biologically-related with such kindness. But Fa Sheng did so, and applied the practices of filiality to a stranger. Does this count as a break with tradition, or continuity with filial tradition? I say both. It's a "moral" act, a "conventional" act in the sense of continuities of conventions of filiality.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Virtues of the Buddhist nuns include: learnedness, compassion, charity, asceticism in food and dress.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: Self-immolation was seen as a very courageous act.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes

Notes: The nun Hui Hsu was lauded for these qualities: "High-minded and distant in character, in physical appearance she looked like a man rather than a woman. Her statements and

opinions were extremely straightforward without the slightest circumlocution." Tsai, 81.

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Learnedness

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Full sexual abstinence was practiced, not partial

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting was not necessary per se, but many nuns (and monks) practiced asceticism in relation to food. For instance, the nun Kuang Ching gave up cereals and ate only pine resin for fifteen years (perhaps a Daoist immortality practice.) The nun Ching Ch'eng gave up rice and millet, and instead ate sesame and mountain thistle. Seng Meng ate only coarse rice and plain vegetables. Pao Hsien gave up cereals and ate arrowroot and taro. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Asceticism in food involved not eating meat, a vegetarian diet

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Mutilations were not required per se, but some nuns engaged in self-mutilation. For instance, the nun Nun Feng burned six fingers to stumps. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*. The practice of burning the body also could be seen in practices of self-immolation, which a number of nuns engaged in.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Painful physical positions do not seem to be a requirement per se, but sitting still (meditation) was a practice. Some nuns were extolled as exemplary for being able to sit very still, such that their body was like wood or stone. See the nuns Seng Kuo, Hui Su and Fa Pien. In her introduction, Kathryn Tsai elaborates: "Meditation was the heart of Buddhist monastic life. The biographer lauds many women for their ability to enter the meditative state, but, in those biographies where a physical description of the meditating woman is given, we find that the woman has entered a trance state of which other Buddhists of the time disapproved. The body of the woman in a trance was like wood or stone, rigid and inflexible, and her companions easily mistook her trance for death (#29). This kind of trance points away from Buddhism and toward the Taoist belief in a seeming death as a doorway to immortality. Once again Buddhism and Taoism are intermingled." (Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 11)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Self-sacrifice is not required, but a number of nuns practiced self-immolation in the name of the Buddha. They would consume fragrant oils to prepare their bodies for burning (the oils made their bodies more susceptible to fire). This is a novel practice in China, but it follows upon a long tradition of women's self-sacrifice for "pro-social" reasons -- in the 1st century *Lie Nu Zhuan*, those reasons would have centered upon the institution of the family or the familial dynasty. Kinney, *The Exemplary Women of Early China*.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Upon entering the order of nuns, one does leave behind attributes of familial wealth, if there was any. However, there were entanglements between families and the order -- and families would at times have donated wealth or sponsored the construction of buildings.

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Upon entering the order, time was spent and ordered differently, vis-a-vis life in the family. Nuns spent a lot of time meditating, chanting sutras, etc. It's not clear that this should be framed as a "sacrifice" of time, however. Their lives in the family would have been differently ordered (it would have been attentive to aspects of family life like raising children or attending to elderly parents) -- but that too is a kind of ordering of time.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Taking precepts were an important part of entering the order. The first nun listed in the biographies, Ching Chien, took the ten precepts with 24 other women of like mind, and this was bestowed by a monastic instructor. It is of interest that foreign monks supported the nuns, whereas Chinese monks were much less helpful. In the biography of Ching Chien: "In the hsien-k'ang reign period (335-342) of Eastern Chin the Buddhist monk Seng-chien, when in the land of the Scythians in central Asia, got hold of a nuns' rites and rules book of the Mahasanghika Buddhist sect. In the first year of the sheng-p'ing reign period (357), the translation of the text was completed in Lo-yang on the eighth day of the second month (in honor of the Buddha's entry into final nirvana). The foreign Buddhist monk T'an-mo-chieh-to set up a ceremonial dais [on which Ching-Chien and her disciples were to accept all of the monastic rules for women as found in the newly translated text.] The Chinese monk Shih Tao-ch'ang objected to this action, however, on the basis of scriptures on the origins of monastic rules that said, because there was no Assembly of Nuns in China to bestow the rules on the women as the scriptures required, the ritual should not be carried out. His objections were not acknowledged and, as a result, [Shih Tao-ch'ang] took a boat down the Ssu River to the south. Ching-chien and the others, four together, became Buddhist nuns by accepting, from the Assembly of Monks only, the obligation to observe all the monastic rules. Ching-chien is thus the first of the Buddhist nuns in China." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 19.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Vegetarian diet

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Hair was cut upon entering the Buddhist order -- ie practices of tonsure.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Secular garb was cast off, in favor of robes

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: The monks and nuns looked to books of rites and rituals from Central Asia and India, and these would have been in non-Chinese languages (Sanskrit). Translation was a main activity at the time.

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Upon entering the order, nuns left behind their natal family names and surnames. They adopted new surnames, with Buddhist resonance -- for instance Shih (clan of the Sakyas) or Seng (monk) or Fa (law).

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: The nuns of the biographies all have changed names. There may have been other nuns without changed names, but they don't show up in the compilation.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The women of the biographies can be found assisting each other in a time of great social turmoil. There is not institutionalized charity to a populace as far as I can tell - the nuns rather rely on a populace to support them, through begging for alms. Sometimes they beg for food on behalf of each other -- as Fa Sheng did for Madame Shan. Or, the nun Shan Miao hosted her natal sister in her abode,

when the sister was widowed; Shan Miao was able to beg for her own food, so that she didn't have to eat food her sister made. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 48, 52.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Many nuns were in close relationship to wealth patrons, see following note.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Nuns would beg on behalf of others. For example, Fa Sheng begged medicines on behalf of Madame Shan, a woman who fell through the cracks of the usual family structure (she had no husband, parent, or son). Ling Tsung lived "during a time when the people suffered a plague and the destitute were numerous." She helped unstintingly. "She fled neither obstacles nor distances to do what she could to help the needy; those who relied on her were many. Because she herself also endured hunger and privation, her own appearance became haggard and careworn."

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There were intimate relations between the monasteries and wealth patrons. For instance, this can be seen in the biography of the nun Hui Chun: "The chief minister of the Sung state, the Chiang-hsia prince, I-kung (413-465) [the fifth son of Emperor Wu], especially respected her and without fail supplied clothing and medicine for her throughout the year. Hui-chun did not keep these goods for herself but used them to build up the convent; the completion of Bamboo Garden was her achievement." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 61. In the biography of Seng Shu: "When the great Liang dynasty came to power, and the empire once again was established in order and good principles, both religious and laity paid her great respect, gathering like clouds from the four directions, but Seng shu did not store up any of the material goods offered to her. Rather, she distributed them as soon as she received them. Sometimes she used the wealth she received to help the Buddhists of the four groups – the monks, nuns, laymen, and laywomen. Sometimes she used it to buy freedom for captured animals. She begged for donations to commission five golden images, all of which were of magnificent beauty. She also commissioned the copying of more than a thousand scrolls of Buddhist scriptures and texts of monastic precepts, the cases and rollers of which were adorned with precious ornaments." Tsai, 102. In the biography of Shih Hui Hui: "Royalty, nobility, and commoners all greatly respected her, coming from everywhere to bestow gifts in great number throughout the year. The wealth that she received she used for copying scriptures, making images, and distributing as alms wherever appropriate. At that time someone, whose name has not come to light, renovated Joyful Peace Convent, refurbishing everything so that it looked new." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 104

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: The virtues extolled in the exemplary nuns had them caring for the elderly -- for instance Fa Sheng's care for the widow Madame Shan. The nuns were innovative in that they at least tried to take care of each other, of friends who were women. The Confucian system meant that the elderly and infirm were meant to be taken care of by family structures. The Buddhist innovation was that care

could be given to non-biological relations -- and so the monastery provided a refuge for the orphaned, widowed, and childless.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Confucian system meant that the elderly and infirm were meant to be taken care of by family structures. The Buddhist innovation was that care could be given to non-biological relations -- and so the monastery provided a refuge for the orphaned, widowed, and childless.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the nuns in their biographies received their education and training within the contexts of their natal homes. But since the sangha was a site of reading, chanting, translation, etc., it was a place where education was valued. Many nuns were also teachers with many students or followers.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Many Buddhist nuns received their literati education in the context of their natal families. The monastic setting would have provided an educational function for orphans, for instance, who were taken in.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Nuns were answerable to the Assembly of Monks. Later, nuns came to be answerable as well to an Assembly of Nuns. How this came to occur can be seen in detail in several biographies. **** The monk Fa Shih said to Ching-chien, the first nun listed in the biographies: "Foreign Buddhists say that nuns

have five hundred rules to follow as compared to fewer for monks, and that must be the difference. I asked the instructor about this, and he said that the rules for nuns are highly similar and only slightly different from the monks' regulations, but, if I cannot get the complete texts of these rules, then I certainly cannot bestow on women the obligation to observe them. A woman aspiring eventually to become a nun may, however, receive the ten fundamental precepts from the Assembly of Monks only, but, without a [female] monastic instructor to train her in the practice of all the rules, a woman has no one on whom to rely [for that training which prepares her to accept the obligation to observe all the rules of monastic life.] Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 18 "In the hsien-k'ang period (335-342) of Eastern Chin the Buddhist monk Seng-chien, when in the land of the Scythians in central Asia, got hold of a nuns' rites and rules book of the Mahasanghika Buddhist sect. In the first year of the sheng-p'ing reign period (357), the translation of the text was completed in Lo-yang on the eighth day of the second month [in honor of the Buddha's entry into final nirvana]. The foreign Buddhist monk T'an-mo-chieh-to set up a ceremonial dais [on which Ching-chien and her disciples were to accept all of the monastic rules for women as found in the newly translated text.] The Chinese monk Shih Tao-ch'ang objected to this action, however, on the basis of scriptures on the origins of monastic rules that said that, because there was no Assembly of Nuns in China to bestow the rules on the women as the scriptures required, the ritual should not be carried out. His objections were not acknowledged and, as a result, [Shih Tao-ch'ang] took a boat down the Ssu River to the south. Ching-chien and the others, four altogether, became Buddhist nuns by accepting, from the Assembly of Monks only, the obligation to observe all the monastic rules. Ching-chien is thus the first of the Buddhist nuns in China." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 19. In the later biography of Seng Kuo (#27) – a number of nuns arrive from Sri Lanka, thus setting up an Assembly of nuns. "In the sixth year of the yuan-chia reign period (429), a foreign boat captain named Nan-t'i brought some Buddhist nuns from Sri Lanka to the capital of the Sung dynasty. The Sri Lankan nuns stayed at Luminous Blessings Convent. [Four years later] in the tenth year (433), Nan t'i, the ship captain, brought eleven more nuns from Sri Lanka, including one named Tessara. The first group of nuns, who by this time had become fluent in Chinese, requested the Indian missionary monk Sanghavarman to preside over the ritual for bestowing the monastic rules on women at the ceremonial platform in Southern Grove Monastery. That day more than three hundred women accepted once again the full monastic obligations [this time from both the Assembly of Monks and the Assembly of Nuns.] Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 54.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Some elite nuns had the ear of state officials, even the emperor or his sons. So elite nuns as teachers interfaced with the institution of the state via their politically engaged students or pupils. Some nuns were still in relationship with their natal family.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddhist nuns belonged to a civilization that grew up along the riverine systems of the Yellow River, the Huai, and the Yangtze River Delta.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Travels of pilgrims occurred alongside the travels of merchants and also officials of empire. This would have occurred along the Silk Routes to the West, and also the maritime Silk Routes. For instance, the nuns from Sri Lanka came with a boat captain Nan Ti.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: There are no taxes or tithes per se, but there was begging for alms. Also, donations were made by wealthy patrons. Nancy Steinhardt notes that "by the Western Jin, officials as well as rulers had become patrons of monasteries, and it had become a practice of those who could afford it to donate their residences for monastery use." Steinhardt, *Chinese Architecture in an Age of Turmoil*, 122.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Monastics were exempt from taxes to the state in the form of labor and crops. Hence a continuing source of tension between sangha and state.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The main social institutions of this time were: the family and the state; the sangha was a new institutional interloper. Though at this time, there is not account of punishment by the state, sanghas were subject to "selections" or culling by the state -- via the criterion of learnedness of its members. In the biography of Chih-Hsien, we have an account of a nun undergoing sangha selection, who was sexually assaulted and stabbed more than twenty times by the depraved administrator doing the selection! Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 22. Later, in the Tang Era, we have an account of a monk executed by waist-chopping, for conducting an illicit affair with a princess, the daughter of Tang Taizong. Kieschnick, *Eminent Monk*, 20.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The nuns were subject to rules and rites. A "rites and rules book of the Mahasanghika Buddhist sect" was first translated in 357 AD -- and the first nuns followed this set of rules and rites. Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 19.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The sangha was in perpetual interaction with the institutions of state and family.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddhist nuns had written language inflected with a lot of translated vocabulary from the Sanskrit. The Chinese language changed a great deal in interaction with Buddhist ideas and practices.

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Literary Classical Chinese pre-existed the entry of Buddhist ideas and vocabulary. But Buddhist vocabulary changed Classical Chinese significantly. So here we have a case study for language's change or evolution.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Food is begged for as alms. Some nuns foraged for food. The biographies do not speak of nuns farming or cultivating their own food -- but then this may be because the nuns of the biographies were fairly elite.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Patrons would give material goods to the nuns to support them. In a footnote, Tsai remarks: "Emperor Wu established the economic institution of the Inexhaustible Treasury to handle the goods and money donated by the faithful to religious institutions. Such great surpluses were built up that the treasuries became major centers of capital accumulation that in turn could be used to finance further religious activities and also be used to make loans. These inexhaustible treasuries became very large and important in the Tang dynasty." Tsai, *Lives of the Nuns*, 145-146, note 43.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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